

SWOT ANALYSIS OF CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITIES IN LEATHER BASED INDUSTRIES

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Abstract:

Corporate social responsibility is the positive activity that is performed by any company, business or organization that affects the employees, society, local authorities, environment and economy positively. This responsibility is accomplished to gain trust, uphold and tenacity from all the shareholders, employees, government, society and potential investors. It is a motive learning and obligation of employees, directors and all stakeholders in serving others and in the development of the society. It is an ample term concerning what is scrutiny in India. It leads the organization to have sustainable growth and development of the organization, society, and the whole economy. The purpose of this study is to explain the proper meaning and description of Corporate Social Responsibility and its development in India and study the theoretical aspects. We will delve into the modern tendency in the country regarding CSR and its proceeding and global implication. This research is on the different leather-based industries which are on the large and small scale of leather-based industries and also discuss their strategies regarding CSR and what is missing in performing their activities. This study will help in knowing exactly what are the Strengths, Weakness, Opportunities, and Threats (SWOT Analysis).

INTRODUCTION

The leather industry is a very old manufacturing sector producing a broad range of goods such as leather footwear, leather bags, leather garments, and so on. Leather and its products are one of the most traded products globally. The consumption of leather products by humans is very

common and used almost every day. The primary raw material for any leather processing industry is derived from slaughterhouses and waste from the meat industry. This raw material is processed and converted into usable leather in tanneries. The leather tanning industry also involves the usage of many chemicals to convert the raw material into finished products. Thus, the leather industry consumes resources and produces pollutants that are toxic and hazardous to the environment. Chromium is an important heavy metal used in leather, electroplating, and metallurgical industries. Reduction and recycling of the various streams at source appear to be a good approach to dramatically decrease the present quality and quantity of effluent generated by this industry. The use of enzymes and microorganisms for de-hairing and stabilizing could reduce the use of toxic metals and chemicals. The Council for Leather Exports (CLE) is an autonomous non-profit organization, which looks after export promotion activities and the development of the Indian Leather Industry. 3,500 companies are manufacturing/exporting leather and leather products are members of this council. India has trade agreements with Japan, Korea, ASEAN, Chile, etc., and is negotiating Free Trade Agreement (FTA) with the European Union, Australia, etc. (Source IBEF). Exports are projected to reach USD 9.0 billion by 2020 from the past level of USD. 5.85 billion. In Leather Industry giving also a great boost, both domestically and internationally, the domestic market is also witnessing high demand for leather goods. Furniture and automobile industries have introduced a wide range of products and require leather goods in their manufacturing processes.

AN OVERVIEW OF INDIAN LEATHER INDUSTRY AND ITS CSR INITIATIVES

India is the second-largest producer and exporter of footwear and leather garments in the world, the third-largest exporter of saddler & harness in the world. In the Indian economy, the leather industry holds a prominent place for its consistency in high export earnings, leather and leather products from India reached a value of US\$ 5.69 billion during 2018-19. The leather industry is bestowed with an affluence of raw materials as India is endowed with 20% of the world cattle & buffalo and 11% of the world goat & sheep population. The leather industry is an employment intensive sector, providing jobs to about 4.42 million people, mostly from the weaker sections of society. Women's employment is predominant in the leather products sector

with about 30% of shares and added to this are the strengths of skilled manpower, innovative technology, increasing industry compliance to international environmental standards, and the dedicated support of the allied industries. The major production of leather and leather products are located in India are State of **Tamil Nadu** – Chennai, Ambur, Ranipet, Vaniyambadi, Vellore, Pernambut, Trichy, Dindigul and Erode; **West Bengal** – Kolkata; **Uttar Pradesh** – Kanpur, Agra, Noida, Saharanpur; **Maharashtra** – Mumbai; **Punjab**- Jalandhar; **Karnataka** – Bengaluru; **Telengana** – Hyderabad; **Haryana** – Ambala, Gurgaon, Panchkula, Karnal, and Faridabad; **Delhi**; **Madhya Pradesh** – Dewas; **Kerala** – Kozhikode and Ernakulam & Cochin; **Rajasthan** – Jaipur. The product segments of Indian leather and footwear industry, such as Tanning sector in India is about 3 billion sq.ft. of annual availability of leathers, India accounts for 13% of world leather production of leathers. The footwear sector is the second largest footwear producer after China, with an annual production of 2.41 billion pairs. Around 45.48% share in Indian leather and Footwear (leather and non-leather) industry's export in (2018-2019). Leather Garments Sector is the second-largest global exporter, next to Italy, with a global market share of 17%. India's total export of leather garment sector in 2018 - 2019 was 8.23%. Leather goods & Accessories sector Including Saddlery & Harness is the fifth largest global exporter. Industry's total export is a 28% share of Indian leather goods & Accessories sector including saddler & Harness.

INDIA'S EXPORT OF LEATHER & LEATHER PRODUCTS

VALUE IN US\$ Mn

PRODUCTS	2018-2019
Finished Leather	721.73
Leather footwear	2195.45
Footwear components	319.10
Leather Garments	468.48

Leather Goods	1434.24
Saddler & Harness	159.35
Non-Leather Footwear	392.63
Total	5691.00

Source: DGCI&S

Corporate Social Responsibility is understood to be the way firms integrate social, environmental and economic concerns into their values, culture, decision making, strategy, and operations in a transparent and accountable manner and thereby establish better practice within the firm, create wealth and improve society. It is also known as Corporate Citizenship or Corporate Responsibility. The corporate affairs ministry has sought public comments on proposed changes to rules governing Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) policy under the companies' law. "To operationalize the Companies (Amendment) Act, 2019, the Companies (Corporate Social Responsibility Policy) Amendment Rules, 2020 has been drafted for carrying out amendments in the Companies (CSR Policy) Rules, 2014, "the ministry notices Under the companies' law, certain classes of companies have to shell out at least two percent of the average net profits, made during the three immediately preceding financial years, towards CSR activities. The Companies (Amendment) Act, 2019 amended Section 135 dealing with CSR and was published in the official gazette on July 31, 2019. Among other changes in the rules, the ministry has proposed setting up the 'National Unspent Corporate Social Responsibility Fund'. The fund would be utilized to undertake CSR projects in the areas or subjects specified in Schedule VII of the Act. The Unspent CSR amount in terms of provisions of sub-section (5) and (6) of Section 135 of the Act shall be transferred by the company to any fund as specified in schedule VII of the Act, as per the draft rules. Under Section 135, every company having a net worth of at least Rs 500 crore, turnover of Rs 1,000 crore or more, or a minimum net profit of Rs 5 crore during the immediately preceding financial year has to make CSR expenditure.

ROLE OF THE BOARD IN CSR

- Form a CSR committee
- Approve the CSR policy
- Ensure proper implementation of CSR policy
- Ensure that 2% has been spent
- State the reason if the amount is not spent

ROLE OF CSR COMMITTEE

- Three or more directors and at least one independent director.
- Formulate and recommend policy to the Board.
- Recommend activities and amount to be spent.
- Keep a check on policy from time to time.

The role of the board and the role of the committee go hand in hand. They are dependent on each other. One is not complete without another.

THEORIES OF CSR

- **Utilitarian theory:** It is a theory on social cost and idea for functionalism and neo-functionalism. Social cost theory is based upon economic forces which are influenced by non-economic forces. Functionalism theory is related to profit-making.
- **Managerial theory:** A theory related to the political approaches, globalization pressure and domestic political structures.
- **Relational theory:** It is an environmental-related theory. It considers social contract, stakeholders, business, society a global corporate relationship.

CSR Theories and its approaches:

1. Instrumental theory

This theory is related to achieving the economic objective with the help of social activities. It maximizes the long-term value of shareholders and helps in carrying out a strategy for gaining a competitive advantage. It makes efficient and maximum use of resources with dynamic capabilities. It can also be regarded as a marketing tool.

2. Political theory.

It focuses on the use of business power in the political area. It assumes that the organization has a direct link with society. It tells that organization is a citizen and a part of the community.

3. Integrative theory.

This theory deals with managerial issues, societal issues, public and stakeholder management.

4. Ethical theory.

This theory focuses on the right and exact thing to be performed. It focuses not only on human resource management but also keeps a check on rights and protects the environment and take care of future generation and develop with sustainability.

SCOPE OF CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY (CSR)

In many different categories of CSR is extended such as:

Human resource management

- To provide an authoritative explanation
- To provide a safe and friendly working environment
- To value a corporate culture
- To ensure maximum satisfaction to customers

Social Contribution

- The welfare of society
- Good corporate citizenship
- Contribution to local communities and authorities
- Assisting for reconstruction after disaster

Environmental management

- Make use of efficient energy tools
- Recycling of wastes and scrap
- Bio-conservation activity
- Efforts to achieve a low carbon society.

Research Methodology

This research paper is based on secondary data. This study includes CSR activities and their initiatives for the Philanthropy, society, environment and ethical resources of Leather industries. This study is descriptive. This study focuses on the Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats of CSR initiative Leather Industries and their contribution towards society, environmental and ethical comparison of contribution among different kind of sustainable developments.

SWOT ANALYSIS OF CSR INITIATIVES IN LEATHER BASED INDUSTRIES

STRENGTHS

- Easy availability of low cost of labour.
- Availability of raw materials and other inputs.
- Presence of qualified leather technologists in the field.
- Exporter-friendly government policies.
- Existence of more than sufficient productive capacity in tanning.
- Management with business background become quality and environment conscious.
- Massive institutional support for technical services, designing, manpower development, and marketing.
- Exposure to export markets.
- Tax incentives on machinery by Government.
- Well-established linkages with buyers around the world.

WEAKNESS

- Environmental issues.
- The low level of modernization and up gradation of technology and the integration of Developed Technology is very slow.
- Low level of labour productivity due to inadequate formal training/unskilled labour.
- Horizontal growth of tanneries.
- Less number of organized product manufacturers.
- Lack of modern finishing facilities for leather.
- Unawareness of international standards by many players as the maximum number of leather industries is SMEs.
- Difficulties in accessing testing, designing, and technical services.

OPPORTUNITIES

- Abundant scope to supply finished leather to multinationals setting up shop in India.
- Growing fashion consciousness globally.
- Use of information technology and decision support software to help eliminate the length of the production cycle for different products.
- Product diversification - There is a lot of scope for diversification into other products, namely, leather garments, goods, etc.
- Growing international and domestic markets.

THREATS

- The entry of multinationals into the domestic market.
- Stiff competition from other countries. (The performance of global competitors in leather and leather products indicates that there are at least 5 countries viz, China, Indonesia, Thailand, Vietnam, and Brazil, which are more competitive than India.)
- Tariff barriers – Developing countries are resorting to more and more tariff barriers indirectly.
- Improving quality to adapt to the stricter international standards.
- Fast-changing fashion trends are difficult to adapt to the Indian Leather Industries.
- Limited scope for mobilizing funds through private placements and public issues, as many businesses are family-owned.

IMPACT OF CSR

Under the SWOT Analysis of Corporate Social Responsibility in the Leather Based Industry is moreover positively impacts all the related baseline of the Leather-based industry.

Such as

On Organization

- Customer retention
- Stable cash flow

- Less cost of production
- A large number of customers
- Brand image
- Reputation
- Creditworthiness
- Stability

On Society

- Society development
- Educated people
- Equality
- Better brand image in the minds of consumers

On Environmental and Resources

- Safe and pollution-free
- Optimum utilization of resources
- Reduce, reuse and recycle resources
- Energy-efficient resources.

CURRENT TREND IN CSR ACTIVITY

India is the first country in the world to make corporate social responsibility has mandatory, so the corporates have to invest their funds in areas such as environmental, ethical, social, education, poverty, gender, equality and hunger as part of any CSR compliance. The education sector received the maximum funding (38 percent of the total) followed by hunger, poverty, and healthcare (25 percent), environmental sustainability (12 percent), rural development (11 percent). Programs such as technology incubators, sports, armed forces, reducing, reducing inequalities saw negligible spending. The year 2019 will be a promising year of corporate citizenry and impact. Reporting, community engagement, employee training, betterment campaigns, and market feedback are all aligning to support a higher level of CSR

activity than ever before. Taking into account the recent amendments to CSR provisions, industry research estimates CSR compliance to improve and range between 97 to 98 percent by the financial year 2019 – 2020. In the current situation the world getting serious conditions about COVID-19 (Corona Virus Disease 2019) from the end of the year 2019, Amid the COVID-19 outbreak, the Ministry of Corporate Affairs has notified that companies' expenditure to fight the pandemic will be considered valid under CSR activities. Funds may be spent on various activities related to COVID-19 such as the promotion of healthcare including preventive healthcare and sanitation, and disaster management. Keeping because of the spread of novel Coronavirus (COVID-19) in India, its declaration as a pandemic by the World Health Organisation (WHO), and the decision of the Government of India to treat this as a notified disaster, it is hereby clarified that spending of CSR funds for COVID-19 is eligible for CSR activity.

FUTURE STRATEGIES OF LEATHER INDUSTRIES AND ITS CSR ACTIVITY.

The global leather goods market is forecasted to grow at a CAGR of 6.2% during the forecast period (2020 – 2025). Leather goods are highly popular among consumers as they have inherent qualities such as dustproof, fireproof, crack-proof, and durability which is expected to increase the growth of the leather goods market.

- Leather goods are highly popular among consumers as they have inherent qualities such as dustproof, fireproof, crack-proof, and durability which is expected to increase the growth of the leather goods market.
- Moreover, the growing demand for trendy handbags, premium leather wallets, and other leather products is influencing the growth of the leather goods market form the last few years. Growing government support for the leather industry is further driving the market growth. For instance, in India, 100% Foreign Direct Investment is permitted through the automatic route and the government has reduced the excise duty to 6% from 12% on leather footwear (footwear with uppers made of leather) with a retail sale price of more than USD 14.55 per pair.

Corporate Social Responsibility has become an important buzzword in the business world. The practice of CSR has evolved and matured over time. CSR now includes strategic philanthropy, employee volunteerism, cause marketing, disaster response, peer-to-peer fundraising, non-profit board service, and even incorporating social responsibility into core business practices and offerings. The year 2019 was action-packed in terms of CSR. With the companies taking a proactive interest in improving their CSR practices, and the government encouraging them by bringing in various amendments in the CSR Act, it is being predicted that 2020 will be even more dynamic for CSR. It focuses on five different trends that can be expected in CSR in 2020. Such as,

IT FOCUS ON ESG (Environmental, Social and Governance)

In the year 2020, the rise in ESG investments is certain, more and more people are getting aware of their carbon and social footprint, and while they may not be able to indulge themselves completely in activism, they certainly prefer to associate with brands that have a good ethical standing in terms of their ESG impact. ESG investment thus is no more only a philanthropic activity. It is more of a business feature that is a must-have for the brands if they want to sustain in the competitive market.

IT FOCUSES ON INCREASING USE OF RENEWABLE RESOURCES.

The global community, especially the millennials, are calling for serious climate action from businesses. In 2019 the climate change crisis is at its peak at present. We saw several climate action movements including the climate strike in the United Nations. Such movements have compelled the business community as well as the government to embrace renewable energy and reduce emissions. According to the solar mandate, to which new construction homes and commercials are required to have a solar Photovoltaic system as an electricity source from January 1, 2020. This policy across the world are set to inspire more investment in developing, adopting and promoting renewable energy.

IT FOCUSES ON TRANSPARENCY IN PROCESSES

The rising awareness among consumers will create a demand for more transparency in the CSR projects of a company. Digitalization has reduced the cases of corruption and increased transparency in the processes. This includes processes in CSR, there will be introspection on how 5G, AI, Blockchain Technology, etc. can be used to improve the transparency in the system. Therefore, the companies will need to provide a transparent roadmap of activities and progress. All this will help drive collective impact.

IT FOCUSES ON EMPLOYEES ACTIVISM

In 2019, we saw that employees participating in climate strikes, pride week, and so on. In 2020, this trend is set to increase as a greater number of young people enter the workforce. Various studies have shown that employees prefer to work for companies that believe in a cause or have a purpose. Including employees in volunteer work for a social cause helps in getting job satisfaction and improve their retention.

IT FOCUSES ON IMPACT.

Leather Industries raw materials

The global demand for meat will need to find a balance with supply problems arising from a wide range of issues. The more recent development of interest in crops for biofuels can only increase the pressure on land use. These changes raise several issues related to health, food safety, the environment, and poverty alleviation. Overall, those involved in all aspects of the leather industry can be expected to spend more time ensuring that they have secure raw materials supplies.

Tanning Industries

The tanning industry with its wide range of raw materials from all over the globe and its extensive variety of end-user clientele is very complex. Tanneries themselves are likely to develop as more machinery processes like operation reduces labor content and improve consistency in leather quality. Environmental issues will become even more important as the world population grows and urbanizes, and global warming and the need for clean drinking water cause increasing concern.

Footwear Industries

Before considering the future, it is necessary to review the changes in the footwear industry over the past 40 years and the dynamics that brought about these changes. The opportunities to meet new growth in domestic and international markets still require sizeable employment in many countries throughout the world, and these countries will continue to fight for their share in the steadily growing world footwear market for many years to come.

Leather goods and other Leather Products

It is expected that the leather goods industry will be tomorrow's world should make sensible use of available natural resources, be it ore, wood, water, or raw hides and skins. Over the next fifteen years, we should expect the transfer of leather goods production to lower-cost countries to continue, at the same time, the emergence of many local brands in countries. Despite rising costs, it is unlikely that the most prestigious companies will start to outsource their production.

Impact on Duties and Tariffs

It is hard to imagine that the disputes regarding tariffs will be resolved in the next fifteen years. The leather industry and the industries supporting it are so important in terms of exports and employment to so many countries that those countries appear certain to try to help them as much as they can. Protectionism occurs in developing countries despite an argument that says that extensive protectionist policies leave the industry open to excessive price fluctuations, weaken further the very weakest, and are unfair to developing countries who have been helping poorer nations. It is also clear that duties create distortions and therefore great opportunities for those who can "get around" them via corruption, smuggling, misreporting or other means. Throughout the world, there is a very significant movement of raw hides and skins, and footwear, in particular, that is outside the legal systems laid down by governments. The volume and characteristics of the world trade in leather and leather products are such, that it is safe to presume that the efforts to influence trade movements through protectionism of one kind or another will continue.

CONCLUSION

This research paper has discussed the Strength, Weakness, Opportunities, and Threats of leather-based industries and their performance, activities, and initiatives in corporate social responsibility. This study concludes the actual strength, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats are situated positively and also the correctable negative circumstances are taking steps to fulfill the performance and initiatives towards the CSR activity by the corporates' contribution of social, ethical, and environmental among the different kind of sustainable developments. Corporate Social Responsibility is not a monopoly process. It is an on-going process as the company is surviving and its activities are running. In the Modern era, the consumer is an essential element of every business. A company's reputation success and survival are in the hands of society. If the companies will do well so far for the society, environment, government, stakeholders, consumers, and suppliers, etc, then only it will be able to achieve its goals otherwise it will not survive successfully in a long period. Companies are taking initiatives for CSR activities and they know their responsibilities and performance of CSR. The companies are integrating their business models with the CSR activities. Even the report is prepared for CSR activities and in the coming times, it will also be shown in the annual reports. India is the first country in the world to make Corporate Social Responsibility has mandatory. So, the corporate has to invest their CSR spending in different areas of sustainable development. The feedback is all aligning to support a higher level of CSR activity than ever before. With the recent amendments to CSR provisions, industry research estimates CSR compliance to improve and range between 97- 98 percent by the financial year 2019 – 2020.

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